

CLINICAL INDICATORS OF COVID-19 IN PREGNANT WOMEN

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Abstract: *the article discusses the severity of COVID-19 in pregnant women. As a result, studies of COVID-19 patients suggest that the risk of developing severe forms of COVID-19 is slightly higher in patients of the third trimester of pregnancy who also suffer from several concomitant diseases, although severe COVID-19 occurs in any trimester regardless of the presence of extragenital pathologies.*

Keywords: *coronavirus, pregnancy, complications, perinatal center, severe form, gestational age, analysis, extragenital pathology, computed tomography, Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Relevance: Currently, on December 23, 2021, 197,918 confirmed cases of new coronavirus infection have been registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan, with a total of 950 deaths. Since the beginning of the coronavirus pandemic, 2015 pregnant women with COVID-19 have been registered. The addition of coronavirus infection to the main disease of pregnant women increases the severity of the course of somatic pathology, complications of both pregnancy and the outcome of childbirth, lengthening the duration of the patient's stay in the hospital and leading to an increase in severe consequences for both the mother and the fetus.

The purpose of the study: To identify the characteristic features of the course of pregnancy in women with COVID-19 and their outcomes, depending on the duration of pregnancy and the presence of extragenital and genital pathology, including the study of anamnesis and laboratory data.

Materials and methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of the medical records of 60 pregnant women with COVID-19 who were on outpatient and inpatient treatment at the Perinatal Center. The age of pregnant women ranged from 21 to 39 years, the average age was 30 years. The study revealed various extragenital and genital pathologies in

89% of patients, assessed the severity of viral pneumonia and laboratory analysis data in this cohort of patients.

Also, at the same time, the severity of viral pneumonia was studied according to the results of computed tomography (CT) in accordance with laboratory data.

Results and discussion: The study showed that out of 60 pregnant women with a new coronavirus infection in 55 (92%) patients, the diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 infection was confirmed by PCR, and in the remaining cases it was established on the basis of the clinic and the results of computed tomography (CT) of the lungs.

Gestational age according to observations: 6-7 weeks (in 5 women), 10-11 weeks (in 6 women), 13-14 weeks (in 5 women), 17-18 weeks (in 5 women), 23-24 weeks (in 4 women), 25-26 weeks (in 6 women), 29-30 weeks (in 6 women), 32-33 weeks (in 10 women), 35-36 weeks (in 9 women), 37-38 weeks (in 4 women).

Parity: The first pregnancy was registered in 18 women (30%), the second pregnancy in 16 women (27%), the third pregnancy in 9 women (15%), the fourth pregnancy in 15 women (25%), the fifth pregnancy in 2 women (3%).

Burdened obstetric and gynecological anamnesis was detected in 31 women (52%), among them: abortions occurred in 15 people (25%), miscarriages in 12 (20%), ectopic pregnancy in 2 women (3%), this convincingly indicates the failure of a woman's reproductive system. Genital pathology in most cases occurred in the form of nonspecific and specific colpitis (carriers of infections - cytomegalovirus infection, herpes simplex virus, chlamydia, mycoplasmosis genitalium, ureaplasmosis), endocervicitis, and chronic forms of adnexitis and metroendometritis.

The following extragenital pathology was revealed in pregnant women with COVID-19. Approximately 65% of patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 have multimorbidity, the frequency of which increases to 71% in severe COVID-19. Diseases of the cardiovascular system were found in 27 (45%); kidney and urinary tract diseases – in 24 (40%); respiratory diseases - in 15 (25%); diseases of the gastrointestinal tract - in 5 (8%); diseases of the endocrine system - in 11 (18%).

The main complaints of pregnant women were subfebrile body temperature (79%), dry cough (75%), shortness of breath (70%), decreased sense of smell (49%), loss of taste (51%), vomiting (35%), bleeding from the genitals (14%), hemoptysis (5%). Also, sweating, nausea, chills, aching joints and muscles, loss of appetite, dry mouth (12%). According to the results of

computed tomography CT-1 was observed in 13 (22%); KT-2 - 22(37%); CT-3 – 5(8%); CT was not performed in 20(33%).

Interpretation of CT. CT-0 indicates the absence of signs of viral pneumonia; CT-1 is a mild form of pneumonia with areas of "frosted glass", the severity of pathological changes is "25%; CT-2 is a lesion of 25-50% of the lungs; CT-3 is a lesion of 50-75% of the lungs; CT-4 is >75% of the lungs affected. 100% of the examined patients recovered.

Pregnancy outcomes: emergency Caesarean section (CT-3) was performed in 6 patients. All children needed intensive care and were hospitalized in the neonatal intensive care unit with hypoxic CNS damage, clinical syndromes were: depression, motor disorders. All children underwent brain ultrasound. Studying the condition of children at birth, we analyzed Apgar scores on the 1st and 5th minutes of life. The number of children born with asphyxia increased significantly in women with severe lung damage.

Conclusion: A retrospective analysis of the study of medical records in pregnant women with COVID-19 suggests that the risk of developing severe forms of COVID-19 is slightly higher in patients of the third trimester of pregnancy and suffering from several concomitant diseases, although severe COVID-19 occurs in pregnant women in any trimester, regardless of the presence of extragenital pathology. The main complication of pregnancy in the first and second half was the threat of termination of pregnancy. At the same time, attention is drawn to the fact of the presence of anemia (in 89%) of patients, which is clearly associated with nutrition and chronic pyelonephritis (in 25%), indicating the presence of this pathology, starting from childhood. Among the complaints of pregnant women, subfebrile fever prevailed in 89%, dry cough in 69%, decreased sense of smell in 61%. Timely laboratory diagnostics allows you to accurately assess the severity of the condition of pregnant women, calculate the risks of various complications and timely determine the correct treatment tactics for COVID-19 in a particular patient.

Thus, this conclusion shows the need for a deliberate decision on the part of a woman in terms of the expediency of carrying a pregnancy during the COVID-19 pandemic and requires careful pre-pregnancy preparation of both spouses.

LIST OF LITERATURE:

1. Yang Z, Liu Y. Vertical Transmission of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2: A Systematic Review. *American Journal of Perinatology*. 2020;37(1):1055–60. pmid:32403141

2. Thomas P, Alexander PE, Ahmed U, Elderhorst E, El-Khechen H, Mammen MJ, et al. Vertical transmission risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection in the third trimester: a systematic scoping review. *Journal of Maternal-Fetal and Neonatal Medicine*. 2020. pmid:32611247

3. Kasraeian M, Zare M, Vafaei H, Asadi N, Faraji A, Bazrafshan K, et al. COVID-19 pneumonia and pregnancy; a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Maternal-Fetal and Neonatal Medicine*. 2020. pmid:32429786

4. Parastoo Hosseini, Shervin Afzali, Mohammadreza Karimi, Milad Zandi, Arghavan Zebardast, Tayebe Latifi, Alireza Tabibzadeh, Akam Ramezani, Armin Zakeri, Amirmohammad Zakeri, Behnam Abedi, Saber Soltani, Abbas Farahani, The coronavirus disease 2019 and effect on liver function: a hidden and vital interaction beyond the respiratory system, *Reviews in Medical Microbiology*, 10.1097/MRM.0000000000000267, **33**, 1, (e161-e179), (2021).

5. Federica Di Guardo, Flavia Maria Di Grazia, Luisa Maria Di Gregorio, Elisa Zambrotta, Grazia Carrara, Ferdinando Antonio Gulino, Attilio Tuscano, Marco Palumbo, Poor maternal–neonatal outcomes in pregnant patients with confirmed SARS-Cov-2 infection: analysis of 145 cases, *Archives of Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 10.1007/s00404-020-05909-4, (2021).

6. Kumar Ankur, Aparna Prasad, Prashant Jain, Ankit Parakh, Ashish Prasad, Sanjeev Chetry, Neonate Receiving Mechanical Ventilation with Continuous Bubbling Coming Through the Orogastic Tube, *NeoReviews*, 10.1542/neo.22-5-e356, **22**, 5, (e356-e359), (2021).